

A PARAMETRIC INVESTIGATION INTO THE EFFECT OF STITCH PATTERN ON MODE I DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS OF LAMINATED DCB SPECIMENS

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ABSTRACT: A parametric analysis, using finite element method (FEM), is conducted to assess the effect of stitching pattern on suppressing delamination crack growth through the use of through-the-thickness reinforcement in DCB specimens. Based on the stitch models presented by Jain and Mai, a micromechanical model representative of interconnected stitching taking into consideration the surface loop is proposed. The stitches are modeled using a two-node rod element capable of taking only tensile loading. The composite laminate is modeled using a four-node plate element incorporating transverse shear deformation. Various stitching patterns, including plain and zigzag stitching, have been investigated to evaluate the optimal stitching arrangement for designers. The numerical examples presented in this paper indicate distinct differences in stitch failure location and behavior for different stitch patterns. Conversely, the peak crack growth resistance values over all stitch patterns vary negligibly. This suggests that stitch pattern plays little role in determining the resistance to crack propagation. Furthermore, that stitch distribution is a definitive parameter in determining crack growth resistance in stitched laminated composites.

Keywords: stitching, stress intensity factor, DCB, stitch pattern, mode I

1. INTRODUCTION

With their high specific strength and structural efficiency, reinforced carbon-fibre composites have established a multitude of growing applications especially within the aerospace, maritime, automotive and building industries [1]. Despite exhibiting exceptional in-plane strength, resin-based fibre composites have shown an inability to endure localized low velocity impacts in the through-thickness direction primarily due to their poor interlaminar properties. In some applications this factor alone could limit the strength of these composites to that of the brittle resin matrix. However, in recent times, toughened epoxy resin matrices [2] and various forms of 3-D reinforcing architectures [1, 3-4] have been utilized to improve the delamination toughness of laminated composites.

In a review of the effects of stitching, conducted by Dransfield et al [5] and more recently by Mouritz et al [1], it was reported that through-the-thickness stitching can significantly improve some interlaminar mechanical properties. They stated that stitching can reduce free edge delamination and improve G_{IC} by 85% also improving flexural strength by 30%. Furthermore, with little impact on the in-plane strength of the composite, stitching increased buckling loads and was successful in arresting crack propagation. In this review, it was found that stitching pattern is not a critical parameter. Liu et al [6], using stitched laminates subjected to impact loading, concluded that stitching pattern significantly affected the shape of the delaminated area but did not affect its size by any great amount.

To date a good deal of research has been devoted to the formulation of realistic stitch models such as the models proposed in ref. [7-9]. This paper employs a set of nonlinear analytical interconnected and

independent stitch models developed in ref. [8, 9] under mode I crack surface displacement. The independent stitch model assumed that the top and bottom surfaces of the stitched laminate are ground off to remove the surface loop and any associated in-plane waviness [10]. The independent stitch was subjected to an elastic stretching and frictional slip stage. The interconnected stitch model was also subjected to an elastic stretching phase but assumed that the embedded end of the stitch, located at the laminate surface, was fixed. This assumed that the surface loop does not contribute to the elastic stretching of the stitch and correspondingly carries no load. In their paper a uniform bridging traction (distributed load) equivalent to the load supported by individual bridging fibres was employed. This analysis assumed that stitch density was the definitive parameter in determining improvements in crack growth resistance. The effects of stitching pattern were not considered.

To more realistically model stitching, Sun et al [11] used discrete stitches in conjunction with the theoretical stitch models proposed in ref. [8, 9]. Their finite element analysis (FEA) model adopted a shear beam element to examine the effects of stitch distribution in the crack plane. The results of this parametric study concluded that stitch distribution can significantly affect the improvement in delamination crack growth resistance. Furthermore, stitch density and stitch volume fraction, as defining parameters, are not sufficient when predicting the effects that stitching will provide.

In this paper, a finite element modeling scheme was developed to conduct a parametric study on the influence that stitching pattern has on mode I delamination toughness of stitched laminated DCB specimens. The stitches are modeled using a two-node rod element capable of taking only tensile loading. The composite laminate is modeled using a four-node plate element taking into account the transverse shear deformation. The virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [12] is used to calculate the Mode I strain energy release rate (SERR) G_I at the crack tip, which is then transformed into stress intensity factor K_I . Most of the geometrical parameters and mechanical properties in the numerical examples are taken from [8, 11] to compare the present numerical results with both the analytical and numerical results of the literature. The results show that when the stitch line spacing and pitch distance are of a similar value, stitch pattern has little effect on the improvement in crack growth resistance and rather it is stitch distribution which plays a greater role in determining the enhancement that stitching provides.

2. STITCH MODEL

The independent and interconnected stitch models proposed in ref. [8, 9] have been used; the interconnected model has been subsequently modified to take into account the surface loop. The modified interconnected model assumptions and corresponding relations are not reviewed in this paper. For a detailed explanation of the independent stitch model refer to [8, 9]. The load carried by the discrete stitching is given by

$$p(t) = 2\tau\pi d_f [Y_I(t)U_3 U_5 + Y_{II}(t)U'_3 U'_5 U'_7 + \left[\left(H + \frac{F_{oI}}{\tau\pi d_f} \right) (1 - U_5) U_4 U_6 \right] + \left[\left(\frac{L_p}{2} + \frac{F_{oII}}{\tau\pi d_f} \right) (1 - U'_5) U'_4 U'_6 \right]] \quad (1)$$

Where τ represents the interfacial shear stress between the stitch fibre and the matrix, d_f is the stitch fibre diameter, H is half the DCB thickness, Y_I and Y_{II} are the slip lengths of the embedded fibre and surface loop respectively, F_{oI} and F_{oII} represent the loads at the embedded end and surface loop end of the stitch, L_p is the stitch pitch distance. The step functions $U_i (i = 3, \dots, 6)$ and $U'_j (j = 3, \dots, 7)$ in equation (1) are Heaviside step functions.

In the initial stage when the stitch is experiencing elastic stretching, the step functions U'_3 , U_4 and U'_4 take into account whether the slip length exceeds the critical embedded length of the stitch. The step function U_5 is unity when the thread is stretching and zero when the slip zone has reached the surface of the laminate. U'_5 performs the same function as U_5 for the surface loop. The step functions U_6 and U'_6 governs the condition of thread rupture. The step function U'_7 is zero when the slip zone of the entire stitch is fully developed and has a value of unity when the surface loop is stretching.

3. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

3.1 Plate element

According to the first order shear deformation plate theory, the displacement fields for each sublaminates can be expressed as follows

$$u = u^0(x, y) + z\theta_y(x, y), \quad v = v^0(x, y) - z\theta_x(x, y), \quad w = w^0(x, y) \quad (2)$$

Where u , v , w and θ_x , θ_y denote translational displacement components in the x , y and z directions, and rotational components about the x and y -axis's, respectively. The superscript "0" represents the mid-plane of the sublaminates. The continuity conditions of the displacements and rotations along the delamination front between the upper, lower and base sublaminates must be strictly satisfied.

3.2 Stitch element

Each stitch element consists of 2 nodes initially collocated in-between two sublaminates prior to the stitch becoming active. I.e. prior to the stitching being loaded, the length of the stitch is equal to zero. With the application of a load, at the free end of the DCB specimen, the sublaminates are forced apart. As the crack propagates and encounters a stitch, the two stitch element nodes are separated by a displacement δ due to the bridging traction provided by the stitch thread. Furthermore, the stitching thread is assumed to carry only axial tensile loads.

The nonlinear relation between the slippage displacement and force for the stitching thread, proposed in [8] and in equation (1), can be employed to simulate the mechanical behavior of the stitching thread. The stitch element can simply be considered as a tension only rod element with a nonlinear material property. The displacement of the thread, δ , can be given by

$$\delta = \sqrt{(u_i - u_{i'})^2 + (v_i - v_{i'})^2 + (w_i - w_{i'})^2} \quad (3)$$

Where, i and i' refer to the upper and lower sublaminates node locations through which the stitch thread passes.

Based on the assumption above, the element stiffness matrix is:

$$[K] = \frac{F}{\delta} \begin{bmatrix} K_5 & -K_5 \\ -K_5 & K_5 \end{bmatrix} = k \begin{bmatrix} K_5 & -K_5 \\ -K_5 & K_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Where,} \quad K_5 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In equation (4) F is the bridging load carried by the stitch thread. It should be noted that the bridging stiffness should be iteratively obtained because the relationship between the displacement and force of the stitch thread is nonlinear.

4. STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE AND STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR

Using the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT), the strain energy release rate (SERR), G , and stress intensity factor, K , at the delamination crack tip is calculated and employed as the fracture toughness of the delaminating composite.

In this paper only unidirectional DCB specimens are investigated and as a result the components of SERR G_{II} , G_{III} should be equal to zero and can be ignored compared to G_I . It should also be noted that this analysis assumes that the crack propagation front is a straight line. Therefore, the SERR presented in these results is the average value across the span of the crack. The SERR is then conveniently transformed into the stress intensity factor, K , according to the relation [13]:

$$G_I = \frac{K_I^2}{E_0} \quad (6)$$

Where E_0 is the orthotropic modulus. For the derivation of E_0 refer to [8].

5. CALCULATION OF CRACK GROWTH RESISTANCE

For a given delamination crack length Δa , the crack propagation condition is governed by the equality of the net stress intensity factor (K_C) to the intrinsic fracture toughness of the composite (K_{IC}). There are two contributions to K_C , the first is the stress intensity factor due to the applied load, K_a , and the second, K_r , is due to the closure traction of the stitching fiber acting across the crack faces. Hence we have

$$K_c = K_a + K_r = K_{IC} \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) may be rearranged and the crack growth resistance K_R can be defined as

$$K_R(\Delta a) = K_{IC} - K_r(\Delta a) \quad (8)$$

To obtain the crack growth resistance K_R , the applied load corresponding to the critical stress intensity factor at the tip of the crack should firstly be iteratively searched. Then by removing all the stitch elements, the stress intensity factor can be re-calculated by the same geometry and applied load, and this new value of stress intensity factor is K_R .

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Consider a DCB specimen, in figure 1 constructed from unidirectional CFRP, with initial crack length $a_0 = 50.0\text{mm}$ and the total length of the DCB is $L = 110.0\text{mm}$. The width of the specimen is $W = 6.0\text{mm}$. The thickness of the DCB is $2H = 4.0\text{mm}$. The material properties of the DCB and stitch thread are as follows:

Figure 1. DCB Geometry

Figure 2. Schematic of various stitch pattern

Unidirectional DCB specimen:

$$E_{11}=1300GPa, \quad E_{22}=7.7GPa, \quad G_{12}=4.2GPa, \quad \nu_{12}=0.33,$$

$$E_0=10.2GPa, \quad K_m=0.8MPa\sqrt{m}, \quad E_m=4.0GPa, \quad K_{IC}=1.28MPa\sqrt{m}$$

Stitch Thread:

$$E_f=125.0GPa, \quad \sigma_{fu}=3.2GPa, \quad \tau=5MPa, \quad d_f=0.3mm,$$

Where, E_{11} and E_{22} are the longitudinal and transverse Young's Moduli of the unidirectional DCB specimen. G_{12} is the inplane shear modulus, ν_{12} is the longitudinal Poisson's ratio, E_0 is the orthotropic Young's modulus, K_m and E_m are the critical stress intensity factor and the Young's modulus of the unreinforced matrix material respectively. K_{IC} is the critical stress intensity factor for the unstitched laminate. E_f and σ_{fu} are the stitch thread Young's modulus and ultimate tensile strength respectively. τ is the interfacial shear stress between the stitch fibre and the matrix and d_f is the stitch thread diameter. Unless otherwise stated, this data will be used extensively throughout the analysis.

To clearly present the results, we firstly give the definition of several terms that will be used frequently in further discussions. Stitch density S_D represents the number of stitches per unit area, as defined in [8]. It should be pointed out that each stitch is comprised of two threads for the most popular stitch types, such as lock and modified lock stitches. Therefore, the coefficient 2 in equation (1) indicates that two threads per stitch are considered. The term stitch volume fraction, V_f , refers to the volume of all stitches compared to the volume of the DCB specimen. K_∞ , the asymptotic value of K_R , is achieved when the crack wake becomes fully saturated with bridging fibres. Δa refers to the crack propagation increment. L_p represents the distance between consecutive rows of stitching. L_s is the spacing between adjacent lines of stitching. Since this paper is concerned with the effects of stitch pattern, figure 2 outlines the various stitch pattern arrangements. *SS* refers to a staggered stitching pattern in which the first line of stitching has three tows, followed by a second line consisting of two tows; this sequence is then repeated along the stitched portion of the DCB specimen. *SI* is the case where the stitches are located internally in consistent rows of three tows all within the DCB specimen. *SE* refers to the case where two outer lines of stitches are located along the DCB edge.

6.1 $K_R - \Delta a$ curve of DCB specimen with independent stitches

To evaluate the effect of stitching pattern on crack growth resistance, the independent stitch models proposed in [8] were utilized. The critical stress intensity factor for the laminate is

$K_{IC} = 1.28MPa\sqrt{m}$ and it is assumed that this value remained constant across the entire unstitched specimen. In order to observe the differences due to stitch pattern, the stitch volume fraction over all test specimens was kept constant. This is reflected in the *SS* pattern where $L_p = 5.0mm$ as opposed to *SI* and *SE* where $L_p = 6.0mm$. The DCB width, W , remained constant at $6.0mm$ and the diameter of the stitch thread, $d_f = 0.3mm$. These dimensions are used consistently throughout this paper for the purposes of comparing stitch pattern. Figure 3 shows the results of this analysis. It can be seen that the crack growth resistance initially starts at the unstitched composite laminate toughness, $K_{IC} = 1.28MPa\sqrt{m}$, and rises with crack growth as the crack wake becomes saturated with bridging fibres. The analysis is terminated once the bridging zone is fully saturated reaching K_{∞} . Performing the best of the three patterns is the *SI* pattern. This may be attributed to a lower load experienced by the central stitch line due to a smaller stitch line spacing L_s i.e. the applied load is more evenly distributed by the bridging fibres. By reducing L_p , to maintain constant V_f , the *SS* pattern performs comparably to the *SE* pattern but does not provide any increase in crack growth resistance. The results show that stitch pattern does not affect, to any great extent, the peak crack growth resistance values for independent stitching. Sun and co-authors [11] stated similar conclusions ascribing the result to the relatively small loads experienced by independent stitching.

Figure 3. $K_R - \Delta a$ curve for independent stitching with various stitch patterns and const V_f .

6.2 $K_R - \Delta a$ curve of DCB specimen with interconnected stitches

Jain et al [8] presented DCB specimens where the crack closure tractions provided by the stitches were represented by a distributed load acting in the crack wake. Similar to this, in order to verify the interconnected model with the analytical results presented in [8], a number of DCB specimens were analysed. Only the *SE* stitch pattern is used in this comparison. To improve the accuracy of the converged value for K_R , particularly at the point of stitch failure, a smaller crack propagation increment, Δa , was used. The same DCB dimensions used in the independent stitch analysis are once again used here.

6.2.1 Comparison of interconnected stitch models

Figure 4 exhibits the results for various FEA models with constant volume fraction of stitching fibres. The analytical model proposed in ref. [8] considers the support ahead of the crack front as being infinitely rigid and that there is no shear deformation, i.e. the DCB specimen is analyzed as a rigidly fixed cantilever beam in pure bending. The model presented in [11] assumes a more realistic approach with the support condition at the crack front being elastically supported. This model goes further to replace the distributed load in [8] with discrete stitching. Similar to [11] the model proposed in this paper models the stitching discretely taking into consideration the surface loop. For this reason, L_p and L_s are made sufficiently small such that the discrete stitching behaves analogous to stitching uniformly distributed in the crack plane. All results presented here, for the interconnected stitches, are prior to the first stitch breaking.

Figure 4. $K_R - \Delta a$ curve for interconnected uniform stitches using various stitch models.

For this analysis, the stitch density is $S_D = 1/30\text{mm}^{-2}$, $d_f = 0.3\text{mm}$, pitch distance $L_P = 1.0\text{mm}$ and stitch line spacing is 1.0mm . It can be noted that the crack growth resistance K_R initially increases from the composite toughness $K_{IC} = 1.28\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, with crack growth Δa , then attains an asymptotic value K_∞ due to the crack wake becoming saturated with bridging fibres. However, at $K_R = K_\infty$ there is a significant difference in the value of crack growth Δa . For the analytical solution this occurs at 6.5mm , the FEA shear beam model at 9.0mm , the plate element model using the stitching model proposed in [8] at 8.5mm and the present plate element model at 9.25mm . The significant increase in the saturated crack growth exhibited in the FEA results can be attributed to the inclusion of the shear effect as well as the difference in the support conditions at the crack tip. Rigidly clamped for the analytical model but elastically supported for all FEA models. The asymptotic value, K_∞ , using plate elements is higher than the analytical model with the present model providing a noticeable increase due to the inclusion of the surface loop. This can be attributed to the relatively small pitch distance coupled with the increased fibre extensibility provided by the surface loop. These two factors combined increases the number of bridging fibres in the crack wake thereby facilitating a higher peak value of K_R . When compared to the independent stitch model, the most significant differences appear in the length at which crack zone becomes saturated as well as in K_∞ , which for the independent

stitches is significantly lower. This is due to the assumption that, for interconnected stitching, the embedded end is fixed at the laminate surface whereas the independent stitch is allowed to pullout.

6.2.2 Effect of stitching pattern

Figure 5 represents the $K_R - \Delta a$ for interconnected stitches superimposing the results for all three stitching patterns. Each DCB specimen was modeled with the same number of stitches, i.e. V_f is constant, with the *SS* pattern performing well to arrest crack growth rapidly. For the *SS* pattern, at $\Delta a = 5.0\text{mm}$ the crack encounters only two lines of stitching, this produces a slightly lower gradient compared to the *SI* and *SE* patterns. At $\Delta a = 10.0\text{mm}$, the *SS* pattern encounters a third row of three tows at which point K_R grows more rapidly until the crack wake is fully saturated reaching K_∞ at $\Delta a = 14.9\text{mm}$. Similarly, the *SI* and *SE* patterns encounter a third row of stitching at $\Delta a = 12.0\text{mm}$ forcing the gradient of K_R to increase more rapidly than the *SS* pattern due to a greater number of stitches in the crack wake. Saturation for the *SI* and *SE* patterns does not occur until $\Delta a = 14.5\text{mm}$ and $\Delta a = 14.3\text{mm}$ respectively. In terms of failure behaviour of stitches, when the stitches are located on the edge, flexing of the DCB specimen spanwise increases the loads in the central stitch line causing the centre stitch, closest to the crack front, to fail first. Further crack growth results in the subsequent failure of the remaining stitches. A more evenly distributed stitch pattern, like the *SI* pattern, exhibits a more predictable failure behaviour with all three tows closest to the crack front failing almost simultaneously. The *SS* pattern shows a failure of two consecutive rows closest to the crack propagation front. Although the various patterns investigated differ invariably, the overall effect of stitch pattern can be seen to be minor with no significant enhancement in the peak value of K_R , especially when considering patterns with similar pitch distances, stitch line spacing and stitching densities. This implies the designer may use any of the three patterns without sustaining any significant penalties. Performing the best of the three patterns in terms of peak crack growth resistance is the *SI* pattern. The *SI* pattern will now be further examined.

Figure 5. $K_R - \Delta a$ curve for various stitch patterns, constant V_f .

6.2.3 Effect of stitch distribution

Utilizing the internally located stitch pattern, Figure 6 Shows the effect of stitch distribution when the stitch volume fraction is kept constant and the stitch density is varied. To accomplish this the stitch

fibre diameter was adjusted to comply with variations in stitch line spacing and pitch distance. It can be seen that by increasing L_p and decreasing L_s the crack growth resistance K_R is substantially improved. Comparing the cases where $L_p = 12.0\text{mm}$, $L_s = 1.0\text{mm}$, $d_f = 0.3\text{mm}$ with $L_p = 6.0\text{mm}$ and $L_s = 2.0\text{mm}$ and $d_f = 0.3\text{mm}$ it is clear that the same stitch density, S_D , but different stitch distribution can produce highly dissimilar results. Although a longer pitch distance can incur a considerably higher improvement in K_R the secondary result is an excessively long crack wake. Although the peak K_R value is of great importance, the efficiency of the stitch distribution must be such that crack propagation is brought to an abrupt end as abruptly as possible. This efficiency can be seen in Figure 6. At $\Delta a = 14.0\text{mm}$, the improvement in crack growth resistance, for $L_p = 6.0\text{mm}$, is almost twice (1.78) that for $L_p = 12.0\text{mm}$. Having identified this area of interest, the designer may not consider this as such a big concern. For the case where $L_p = 1.0\text{mm}$, $L_s = 2.0\text{mm}$ and $d_f = 0.1225\text{mm}$, K_∞ is 4.9 times greater than K_{IC} with stitch failure occurring at $\Delta a = 10.0\text{mm}$. However, in terms of design and bearing in mind the stitching process, having this number of stitch fibres inserted into the laminate may be detrimental to the in-plane properties of the DCB specimen. Although not represented, the *SE* and *SS* patterns perform in much same fashion when the pitch distance and stitch line spacing are altered. To an extent, these results substantiate the ideas presented in [8]. However, the stitch pattern is not a critical parameter in the improvement of crack growth resistance, rather more concern should be focused towards stitch distribution not in terms of stitch density but more so in the form of pitch distance and stitch line spacing control.

Figure 6. $K_R - \Delta a$ curve for *SI* pattern including the surface loop, const V_f with varying pitch distances and stitch line spacing.

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper utilizes a finite element plate model to predict the effect of through-the-thickness reinforcement, in the form of stitching on Mode I delamination toughness of DCB specimens. Applying the independent stitch model proposed in [8] as well as a modified interconnected stitch model accounting for the surface loop, the effect of stitch pattern was examined. The results show that the surface loop contributes to a slight improvement in

interlaminar fracture toughness. But more importantly, stitch pattern plays no significant role in the improvement in crack growth resistance for stitched DCB specimens specifically when the pitch distances and stitch line spacing are similar. However, when stitch density is maintained constant and stitch pitch distance and stitch line spacing are altered, the results are distinctly different. This implies that stitch distribution is a critical parameter in determining the improvement in crack growth resistance of stitched laminated composites.

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REFERENCES

1. Mouritz A. P., Bannister M. K., Falzon P. J., Leong K. H., "Review of applications for advanced three-dimensional fiber textile composites", *Composites A*, 30 (1999), pp1445-1461.
2. Kim J., Baillie C. Poh J., Mai Y.-W., "Fracture Toughness of CFRP with Modified Epoxy Resin Matrices", *Composites Science and Technology*, v43 (1992), pp283-297.
3. Carvelli V., Poggi C., "Numerical Prediction of the Mechanical Properties of Woven Fabric Composites", *ICCM-13*, June25-29 (2001), pp1-9.
4. Tazawa Y., Watanabe N., Ishikawa T., "Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of 3D orthogonal interlocked fabric Composites", *Composites Science and Technologies*, 59 (1999), pp1262-1270.
5. Dransfield K., Baillie C., Mai Y.-W., "Improving the delamination resistance of CFRP by stitching — a review", *Composites Science and Technology*, 50 (1994), pp305-317
6. Liu D., "Delamination Resistance in Stitched and Unstitched Composite Plates Subjected to Impact loading", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, v9, January 1990, pp59-69.
7. Cox B. N., "Constitutive Model for a Fiber Tow Bridging a Delamination Crack", *Mechanics of Composite Materials and Structures*, 6 (1999), pp117-138.
8. Jain L. K., Mai Y.-W., "On the effect of stitching on Mode I delamination toughness of laminated composites", *Composites Science and Technology*, 51 (1994), pp331-345.
9. Jain K. L., Wetherhold R. C., "Effect of Fibre Extensibility on the Fracture Toughness of Short Fibre or Brittle Matrix Composites", *Applied Mechanics Review*, v45 (8) (1992), pp377-389.
10. Farley G. L., Dickinson L. C., "Removal of Surface Loop from Stitched Composites Can Improve Compression and Compression-after-Impact Strengths", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 11 (1992), pp633-642.
11. Sun X., Tong L., Wood M. D. K., Mai Y.-M., "Effect of Stitch Distribution on Mode I Interlaminar Fracture toughness of Laminated DCB Specimens", *Composite Science and Technology*, (Submitted for Publication).
12. Rybicki E. F. and Kanninen M. F., "A finite element calculation of stress intensity factors by modified crack closure integral". *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 9 (1977), pp931-938.
13. Sih G. C., Paris P. C. and Irwin G. R., "On the cracks in rectilinearly anisotropic bodies", *International Journal of fracture*, 1 (1965), pp189-203.